

ISic1175

Halaesa honours Diogenes Lapiron, son of Diogenes

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

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Principal Contributor

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Autopsy

2017-07-21 (Prag)

Last Change

2019-02-06 - Jonathan Prag fully revised the file based upon autopsy and new edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

First recorded by Antonio Agustín, c.1559, who saw it in the Church of Santa Maria dei Palazzi, Halaesa

Coordinates

37.996451, 14.261885

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8786

Physical Description

A block of white limestone. The block is intact, but has suffered considerable loss to the front left edge and upper front left corner, as well as general degradation of the lower front edge and lower front right corner; the rear upper right corner is also missing. The upper surface shows traces of something being placed on top, but since the stone was apparently reused in the wall of the church, it is hard to know what is original.

Dimensions

Height 28 cm

Width 57.5 cm

Depth 59 cm

Layout

Five lines of Greek text are preserved, with some of the initial letters lost at the left margin.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are plainly and evenly cut, and well spaced, without serifs. Epsilon has a short middle bar, omicron is full size, omega is open.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-5: 25-30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. [θ]εοῖς πᾶσι
2. [ὁ] δᾶμος τῶν Ἀλαισίνων
3. [Δι]ογένην Διογένεος

4. Λαπίρωνα
5. [εὐ]εργεσίας ἔνεκεν

Apparatus

Text of Prag from autopsy

Translation (en)

The people of the Halaesini (dedicate) to all the gods (a statue of) Diogenes Lapiro son of Diogenes on account of his beneficence.

Translation (it)

Il popolo degli alesini (dedica) agli dei tutti (una statua di) Diogene Lapiro figlio di Diogene per la sua beneficenza.

Commentary

The inscription has the form of a standard honorific dedication for an individual, and there are several similar texts from the area of the agora at Halaesa. Several other individuals are known from Halaesa with the second name 'Lapiron' (in three other inscriptions, ISic1176 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1176>] , ISic0800 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0800>] , ISic3571 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3571>] and from Cicero, *In Verrem* 2.2.19-28), and the name Diogenes is recorded a second time in the same family in ISic1176 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1176>] - in theory this could be the same individual (see Facella 2006: 229-241 on the family). The name Lapiron is otherwise only attested at Locri (SEG 32.1018 [http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1874-6772_seg_a32_1018]), although the phenomenon of such second names is common in Hellenistic Sicily (O. Masson, *Onomastica Graeca Selecta* (2000), vol. 2, 379-86). This block is most likely to be the base, or part of the base, for a statue or some other object dedicated to 'all the gods' in honour of Diogenes.

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